

CNN	38	CNN																														
Part-of-Speech	8	34	Part-of-Speech																													
LSTM	13	9	31	LSTM																												
Bi-LSTM	11	5	4	20	Bi-LSTM																											
RNN	11	5	10	4	18	RNN																										
GRU	9	4	6	3	5	17	GRU																									
SVM	1	3	1	0	0	1	18	SVM																								
BERT	1	8	4	2	0	2	1	15	BERT																							
Word2Vec	5	5	3	4	3	4	2	0	13	Word2Vec																						
Glove	3	2	5	2	3	4	1	0	3	11	Glove																					
Random Forests	1	2	0	0	0	1	6	0	1	1	7	Random Forests																				
BiGRU	2	2	1	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	6	BiGRU																			
Naive Bayes	1	0	1	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	1	0	6	Naive Bayes																		
K-means	1	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	1	2	1	0	0	6	K-means																	
GCN	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	6	GCN																
LDA	1	1	0	0	0	1	2	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	6	LDA															
TF-IDF	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	1	2	0	2	2	0	0	6	TF-IDF														
Information aggregation	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	6	0	0	6	Information aggregation													
n-grams	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	5	n-grams													
KNN	1	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	4	KNN												
CRF	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	4	CRF										
SentiWordNet	0	3	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	SentiWordNet										
Logistical Regression	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	3	Logistical Regression									
Sent2Vec	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	3	Sent2Vec								
DNN	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	DNN								
Gibbs sampling algorithm	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	Gibbs sampling algorithm								
Ablation experiment	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	Ablation experiment						
Vader-Lexicon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	Vader-Lexicon						
DBN	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	DBN						
Bag-of-words model	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	Bag-of-words model						
Multi-criteria decision-making	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	Multicriteria decision-making			
Mutual information	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	Mutual information		
RoBERTa	4	0	2	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	RoBERTa	
TextRank	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	14	TextRank	
Aho-Corasick automaton	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	Aho-Corasick automaton